

Effect of some Organotin Halides, Pseudohalides and their Complexes on Oxidative Enzymes and CNS Activities

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Several di- and triphenyltin(IV) halides and pseudohalides have been screened for their gross CNS activity (*in vivo*) and for monoamine oxidase and pyruvate oxidase inhibitory activities (*in vitro*) in rat. The compounds were found to be CNS depressants. Ph_2SnCl_2 , Ph_2SnCl and Ph_2SnNCS have shown significant inhibition against both the tested enzymes.

UNLIKE tin and its inorganic derivatives, organotins are reported to possess noteworthy biological activities¹. The toxicity, gross CNS activity and oxidative enzymes inhibitory powers of organotins, particularly, triphenyltin pseudohalides and their complexes, have not been studied so far, hence we are reporting the same in this communication. But much has been known regarding the neuropharmacological significance of organic Lewis bases², used herein for complexation.

The four title organotin halides and pseudohalides and eight of their complexes designated by the general formula Ph_2SnX , $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnX}'$, $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnN}_2\cdot\text{L}$ and $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnNCS}\cdot\text{L}'$ [$\text{X}=\text{N}_3$, Cl , NCS ; $\text{X}'=\text{Cl}$; $\text{L}=2,6$ -lutidine, $2,4,6$ -collidine, 2 -methylimidazole, 1 -methyl- 2 -piperidinone, N,N' -diethylacetamide, $1,1,3,3$ -tetramethylurea, tetramethylene sulphoxide; L' =tetraethylammoniumbromide (C_2H_5)₄NBr] have been screened *in vitro* for their toxicity and gross CNS activities on the brain of albino mice and for MAO and pyruvate oxidase inhibitory activities on rat brain sucrose homogenate.

Experimental

The compounds Ph_2SnX and $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnX}'$ were prepared by the reported methods³. We have already reported⁴ the preparation and characterisation of triphenyltin azido complexes.

In general the adducts were prepared by the direct interaction (refluxed for 2–3 h) of organotin halide and pseudohalide with various Lewis bases (L) in anhydrous acetone. The products were isolated either by distilling off the excess solvent or by the addition of excess of petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) or *n*-hexane followed by repeated washings with the same solvent and drying under reduced pressure and analysed.

Toxicity test and gross CNS activity: The compounds were investigated for their approximate lethal dose in 50% of tested animals. To a group

of 5 albino mice (20–25 g) of either sex the test compounds were injected intraperitoneally at a dose 100 mg/kg. The behavioural changes in gross CNS activities were noted at 1/5th of ALD_{50} . The observations of effects on spontaneous motor activity, reactivity to sound and touch, body temperatures, belly muscles (writhing) and eye lids muscles (ptosis) etc. were noted after 1 h of drug administration. The data are noted in Table 1.

Monoamine oxidase inhibitory activity: A spectrophotometric method was used for the determination of monoamine oxidase activity of rat brain homogenate using kynuramine as the substrate. The 8-hydroxyquinoline formed by the cyclisation of aromatic aldehyde (oxidative deamination products of kynuramine) was estimated⁵ by the spectrophotometric method at 315–380 nm. The compounds were administered at the dose of 100 mg/kg intraperitoneally. The rat brain homogenate in sucrose was used as a source of monoamine oxidase enzyme and the test compounds were dissolved in propylene glycol (100%) and used at a final concentration of $1 \times 10^{-8} \text{M}$. The reaction was started by the addition of the substrate after a preincubation of 5 min at 37°. After an incubation period for 30 min, the reaction was stopped by adding 10% perchloric acid (1 ml) and the precipitated proteins were removed. The optical density of the suitable aliquot of the supernatant was measured at 315–380 nm. The percent inhibition was calculated from the decrease in the optical density change.

Pyruvate oxidase inhibitory activity: Pyruvate oxidase inhibition activity was determined by the method of Cabaud *et al.*⁶. The substrate was sodium pyruvate and pyruvic acid formed was converted to its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine derivatives in alkaline medium and the colour intensity was measured spectrophotometrically at 510 nm. The change in colour intensity after enzyme reaction and that in the presence of test compounds

TABLE 1 - ALD₅₀ AND GROSS ACTIVITIES AND MAO INHIBITORY AND PYRUVATE OXIDASE INHIBITORY ACTIVITIES

Sl. no.	Compd.	ALD ₅₀ * mg/kg i.p.	1/5th of ALD ₅₀ **		MAO Inhibition (%) at 1 × 10 ⁻³ M	Pyruvate oxidase (%) inhibition at 1 × 10 ⁻³ M	
			SMA and react.	Other effects			Body temp. (°C)
1.	Ph ₃ SnN ₃ .DEA	59.9 ↓		Ptois (+)	↓0.4	23.45 ± 0.31	40.31 ± 0.52
2.	Ph ₃ SnN ₃ .1-Me-2-pip	26.1 ↓		Ptois (+)	↓0.9	47.00 ± 0.25	27.40 ± 0.28
3.	Ph ₃ SnN ₃ .TMU	17.8 ↓		(-)	↓0.7	31.43 ± 0.51	42.75 ± 0.25
4.	Ph ₃ SnN ₃ .2-Me-idz	21.5 ↓		(-)	↓0.1	17.45 ± 0.47	21.83 ± 0.61
5.	Ph ₃ SnN ₃ .2,4,6-Coll	38.3 ↓		(-)	↓0.9	44.65 ± 0.31	37.52 ± 0.43
6.	Ph ₃ SnN ₃ .2,6-lut ^a	-		-	-	21.52 ± 0.65	33.50 ± 0.88
7.	Ph ₃ SnN ₃ .TMSO ^a	-		-	-	27.45 ± 0.35	34.84 ± 0.31
8.	[(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ N][Ph ₃ SnNCSBr]	17.8 ↓		Writh (+)	↓0.5	55.01 ± 0.34	35.35 ± 0.43
9.	Ph ₃ SnN ₃	59.9 ↓		pilo (+) body, limbs relaxed	↓0.6	35.44 ± 0.67	22.31 ± 0.53
10.	Ph ₃ SnCl	21.5 ↓		(-)	↓1.2	80.41 ± 0.16	65.43 ± 0.32
11.	Ph ₃ SnCl ₂	17.8 ↓		Writh (+)	↓1.0	82.45 ± 0.95	65.40 ± 0.87
12.	Ph ₃ SnNCS	35.9 ↓		Writh (+)	↓0.3	45.31 ± 0.25	60.35 ± 0.43

*Downward arrows indicate decrease of body temperature.

**SMA = spontaneous motor activity; react. = reactivity; (-) = not affected; (+) = present; writh = writhing; pilo = piloerection.

^aNot screened for ALD₅₀ and gross CNS.

provided a direct measurement of inhibition of pyruvate oxidase at the concentration of 1 × 10⁻³ M of test compounds.

In all the *in vitro* enzymatic activities, the blank experiments were performed in presence of propylene glycol and the compounds were incubated with the enzymes at 37°. The experiments were done in duplicate and mean values with standard deviations were recorded.

Results and Discussion

The results of the investigation are given in Table 1.

ALD₅₀ and gross CNS activity: The ALD₅₀ of all the compounds ranged between 17.8 and 59.9 mg/kg i.p. All the compounds have induced CNS depressant tendencies in mice at 1/5th of ALD₅₀ of respective compound (SMA and reactivity to sound and touch were decreased). The better CNS depressant effects were exhibited by compounds 1, 2 and 9 (Table 1) inducing ptosis. Writhing was induced by compounds 8, 11 and 12. All the compounds have shown hypothermia on mice in the range 0.1 - 1.2°.

MAO inhibitory activity: The monoamine oxidase inhibitory activity of all compounds at their concentration of 1 × 10⁻³ M in final reaction mixture, ranged from 17.45 ± 0.47 to 82.45 ± 0.95% showing inhibition of MAO of rat brain homogenate. From the data (Table 1), the following correlations may be made. (i) The MAO inhibitory activity is a function of electronegative group attached to central tin atom—more the electronegativity (χ_p) of this group, lesser is the MAO inhibition of organometal molecule. Thus the

decreasing order of MAO inhibition relative to the electronegative substituent along with central tin atom is Cl (χ_p, 2.95) > NCS (4.17) > N₃ (4.42). (ii) When the donating electrons come from the heteroatom which is a part of aliphatic system (more electron availability on donor atom), the complexes have shown better MAO inhibition, relative to the complexes in which donor atom belongs to aromatic system (low electron availability). (iii) The ligation has decreased the MAO inhibition. (iv) A comparison of MAO inhibition by Ph₃SnNCS and its anionic complexes indicates that the anionic complex formation increases the MAO inhibition.

Pyruvate oxidase inhibitory activity: The pyruvate oxidase inhibitory activity of all the compounds ranged between 21.81 ± 0.61 and 65.43 ± 0.32% inhibition at a final concentration of 1 × 10⁻³ M. The following correlations may be made. (i) With regard to the electronegative part around the central tin atom, the activity was found to follow the order Cl (χ_p, 2.95) > NCS (4.17) > N₃ (4.42). (ii) Ligation has generally increased the pyruvate oxidase inhibition (*cf.* the activity of Ph₃SnN₃ and its complexes). (iii) The complexation with anionic ligands has decreased the pyruvate oxidase inhibition.

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References

1. J. M. BARNES and L. MORGAN, *Organomet. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, 3, 137; T. N. SRIVASTAVA, S. N. BHATTACHARYA, S. K. TANDON, J. DAS GUPTA, B. J. JAFRI and O. P. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1968, 8, 65; T. N. SRIVASTAVA, P. C. SRIVASTAVA, S. K. SRIVASTAVA and O. P. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Antibact. Antifung. Agents*, 1981, 9, 439; 1982, 10, 429; T. N. SRIVASTAVA and S. K. TANDON, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1968, 8, 391; J. S. TNAYER, *Organomet. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, 76, 265.
2. J. CASTANER and D. M. PATON, *Drugs Future*, 1978, 3, 800; W. R. MCGRATH and A. HORITA, *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.*, 1962, 4, 178; B. R. PANDEY, K. RAMAN, J. P. BARTH WAL and S. S. PARMAR, *Res. Commun. Chem. Pathol. Pharmacol.*, 1978, 22, 199; G. SANTROCH and L. G. NUMBER, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, 90, 121581; V. K. SRIVASTAVA, B. R. PANDEY, R. C. GUPTA, J. P. BARTH WAL and K. KISHORE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 56, 1024; S. S. TIWARI, R. AGARWAL and R. K. SATSANGI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 1040.
3. J. H. HOLLOWAY, G. P. MCQUILLAN and D. S. ROSS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1971, 1935; R. K. INGHAM, S. D. ROSENBERG and H. GILMAN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1960, 60, 459; J. S. THAYER and R. WEST, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 406.
4. T. N. SRIVASTAVA, P. C. SRIVASTAVA and S. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Met.-Org. Chem.*, 1982, 12, 533.
5. M. KRAJIL, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1956, 8, 191.
6. P. G. CABAUD, F. WROBLEWSKI and V. RUGGIERO, *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.*, 1958, 30, 234.